

COMPARATIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPONENTS IN THE PRODUCTION OF MAKARON PRODUCTS FROM A COMPOSITE MIXTURE

¹Azamatov U.Z., ²Sanayev E.Sh., ³Abrolov A.A.

^{1,2}Tashkent Chemical-Technological Institute

³Fergana Polytechnic Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14598105>

Abstract. Currently, work is underway worldwide to include various grains in the recipe for the production of non-traditional pasta products. The possibilities of using soft wheat, buckwheat, and soybean flour, which are considered such grain additives and have high nutritional value, have been studied. By combining the flour obtained from these grains, it is possible to produce high-quality, nutritious, and non-traditional pasta products. Comparative analysis of raw materials is of great importance in ensuring the technological and nutritional balance between them, and this research aims to expand the production possibilities of non-traditional pasta products. The study of the physicochemical properties of the aforementioned grains allows for the development of an optimal recipe for pasta.

Keywords: non-traditional pasta, food, metal-magnetic mixture, endosperm, soy flour, buckwheat flour, vitamin mineral complex.

Introduction:

Nowadays, there is a growing interest in healthy eating habits among the population. The development of the food industry and the increasing consumer demand for nutritious, high-quality, and natural products necessitate the development of new technologies. Among these, the interest in producing non-traditional food products is on the rise. One significant direction in this field is the production of non-traditional pasta products. These products enhance nutritional value by using raw materials rich in essential micronutrients and vitamins, such as zinc, iron, and protein, thus promoting healthy eating [1].

Pasta is widely consumed globally and constitutes a significant part of food products. Traditional pasta is primarily made from wheat flour, but its relatively low content of protein, vitamins, and minerals poses a challenge. Therefore, selecting raw materials with high nutritional value is essential for the production of non-traditional pasta products. Adding components like buckwheat flour and soy flour not only increases the nutritional value but also allows the formation of new sensory characteristics in the product [2].

Methods and Techniques of Research: The organoleptic indicators of the flour were studied in accordance with GOST 27558–87. The moisture content of the flour and dry wheat gluten was determined according to the method described in GOST 9404–88. The acidity level of the flour was measured using GOST 27493–87. The amount of metallic and magnetic impurities was tested in compliance with GOST 20239–74. The ash content of the flour was analyzed according to GOST 27494–87, while the quantity and quality of raw gluten were determined following GOST 27839–2013.

Figure 1: Nutritional Value of Flours (g/100 g)

Results and Discussion: The results of the nutritional value analysis for the flours (premium wheat flour, buckwheat flour, and soy flour) are presented in Figure 1.

The protein content in premium wheat flour is lower compared to other types. This is due to its composition, which mainly consists of the central parts of the endosperm that are low in protein. The proteins in wheat flour include fractions of prolamins, glutelins, globulins, and albumins. The protein content in premium wheat flour is **10.8 g/100 g**.

Buckwheat flour proteins are rich in lysine and leucine but contain less glutamic acid, proline, and arginine. However, the aspartic acid content is higher compared to other grains, with approximately 56% of these acids present as amides [3]. The main advantages of buckwheat flour are its low glycemic index and the complete absence of gluten proteins. Buckwheat flour contains **13.6 g/100 g** of protein.

Soy flour proteins mainly consist of albumins and globulins, with 58–66% of these being high molecular weight globulins. Soy proteins are more complete in amino acid composition compared to wheat and buckwheat flours, enhancing the nutritional value of food products. The protein content in soy flour is **36.0 g/100 g**, which is 70% higher than in premium wheat flour and 62% higher than in buckwheat flour.

The fats (lipids) in premium wheat flour mainly consist of triglycerides of unsaturated fatty acids: oleic, linoleic (the primary one), and linolenic acids. These acids are considered highly nutritious and possess vitamin-like properties. The fat content in premium wheat flour is **1.3 g/100 g**.

In buckwheat flour, two-thirds of the fat content is made up of unsaturated fats. Its free lipids consist of 55 types of triglycerides, accounting for 13.51% of the total fat mass. Among them, tri-unsaturated triglycerides (50%) and di-unsaturated triglycerides (40%) dominate, while fully saturated triglycerides (mainly palmitic acid) make up only 0.12%. The fat content in buckwheat flour is **1.2 g/100 g**.

Soy flour is a rich source of unsaturated fatty acids (α -linolenic acid – omega-3 and linoleic acid – omega-6). The fat content in soy flour is **10.0 g/100 g**, which is 87% higher than in premium wheat flour and 88% higher than in buckwheat flour.

Premium wheat flour contains fast (simple) carbohydrates, amounting to **69.9 g/100 g**. The carbohydrate composition is dominated by high polysaccharides (starch, cellulose, hemicellulose, pentosans) and small amounts of sugar-like polysaccharides (di- and trisaccharides) and simple sugars (glucose, fructose).

Buckwheat flour contains slow (complex) carbohydrates, amounting to **71.9 g/100 g**. Its carbohydrate composition is dominated by easily digestible sugars and energy-providing substances.

Soy flour also contains complex carbohydrates, but their amount is significantly lower compared to wheat and buckwheat flours. The carbohydrate content in soy flour is **9.0 g/100 g**. In terms of carbohydrate content, buckwheat flour has 7% more carbohydrates than premium wheat flour and 87% more than soy flour.

Fiber Content:

The results of the study on fiber content in flours (premium wheat, buckwheat, and soy flour) are presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Fiber Content in Flours (g/100 g)

Fiber is defined as "nutritional components that are not broken down by the digestive enzymes of the human body but are processed by beneficial intestinal microflora." The importance of fiber is widely acknowledged, with nutritionists consistently emphasizing its inclusion in daily diets. Today, fiber is recognized as an essential component of a healthy diet.

Due to its location mainly in the outer shell of grains, the fiber content in premium wheat flour is relatively low, at **3.2 g/100 g**.

In buckwheat flour, fiber consists of pectin, lignin, cellulose, and hemicellulose, substances known to have cleansing and health-promoting effects on the human body. The fiber content in buckwheat flour is **2.8 g/100 g**.

Soy flour's fiber comes from the seed cell walls and includes polysaccharides, starch, and lignins. The fiber content in soy flour is **5.0 g/100 g**. The ratio of soluble to insoluble fiber ranges from 1:4 to 2:3, meeting human dietary needs. The water-soluble fiber portion (mucilaginous substances) contributes additional health benefits.

Compared to premium wheat flour, soy flour contains **88% more fiber**, and compared to buckwheat flour, it contains **91% more fiber**.

B vitamins are water-soluble and play a critical role in cellular metabolism. Each vitamin in the B group has specific biological significance. Their wide-ranging benefits are crucial for the proper functioning of the body, supporting brain and nervous system cells, protecting against free radicals, and ensuring normal metabolism. Sufficient intake of these vitamins contributes to mental clarity, a good mood, general vitality, and youthful energy.

Vitamin B1 (Thiamine): B1 is essential for carbohydrate, fat, and protein metabolism. The B1 content in soy flour is **1.80 mg/100 g**, which is **90.6% higher than premium wheat flour** and **77.8% higher than buckwheat flour**.

Vitamin B2 (Riboflavin): B2 is necessary for red blood cell and antibody production and plays a role in growth and reproductive functions. The B2 content in both buckwheat and soy flours is the same, at **0.18 mg/100 g**, which is **77.7% higher than premium wheat flour**.

Figure 3: Vitamin B Content in Flours (mg/100 g)

B5 plays a vital role in acetylation and oxidation processes and is involved in carbohydrate and fat metabolism. The B5 content in soy flour is **1.80 mg/100 g**, which is **83.3% higher** than in premium wheat flour. Buckwheat flour does not contain B5.

B6 improves the digestion of unsaturated fatty acids, ensures the normal functioning of muscles and the heart, and aids in their efficient relaxation. Buckwheat and soy flours have nearly the same B6 content, ranging from **0.50 to 0.52 mg/100 g**, which is **66–67% higher** than in premium wheat flour.

B9 assists in cell division and is essential for the development of the immune and cardiovascular systems. The B9 content in buckwheat flour is **0.30 mg/100 g**, which is **90% higher** than in premium wheat flour and **70% higher** than in soy flour.

PP stimulates metabolic processes involving fats and carbohydrates, enabling energy production from these compounds. The PP content in soy flour is **3.34 mg/100 g**, which is **64% higher** than in premium wheat flour and **7% higher** than in buckwheat flour.

Figure 4. The content of vitamins PP, C, E, H, and K in flour (mg/100 g)

Vitamin C (ascorbic acid) is one of the essential organic substances for human health, influencing all vital functions of the body. Ascorbic acid is only found in soy flour, where its amount is 0.660 mg/100 g.

Vitamin E (tocopherol) is one of the most essential vitamins for the body. It is called the "beauty vitamin" because it has a positive effect on the skin, nails, and hair. Additionally, as the body's main antioxidant, it protects cells from the active forms of oxygen. Vitamin E is present in high-quality wheat flour at a concentration of 1.500 mg/100 g, which is 80% more than in buckwheat flour and 77% more than in soy flour.

Vitamin H (biotin) is involved in metabolic reactions and is found in digestive enzymes that are essential for the synthesis and breakdown of fats and proteins. Biotin ensures normal growth, tissue and muscle formation, as well as the proper functioning of energy reactions. Biotin is only found in high-quality wheat flour, where its content is 0.002 mg/100 g.

Vitamin K (phylloquinone) is necessary for the normal process of blood clotting. Phylloquinone is only found in soy flour, where its amount is 0.005 mg/100 g.

Figure 5 presents the research results on the content of micro- and macroelements in different types of flour (high-quality wheat, buckwheat, and soy flour).

Figure 5. The content of micro- and macroelements in flour (mg/100 g)

Micro- and macroelements ensure the normal functioning of the body's major systems (muscles—during muscle contraction, digestive and cardiovascular systems). Their deficiency or complete absence can lead to serious diseases and even the death of the organism.

Fe (iron) participates in the processes of blood formation, normalizes thyroid gland activity, regulates immunity, and participates in tissue respiration. The iron content in buckwheat flour is 4000.00 mg/100 g, which is 70% higher than that in wheat flour and 99% higher than in soy flour.

Zn (zinc) is involved in muscle contraction, is a component of metalloenzymes, and plays an important role in the metabolism of proteins and fats. The zinc content in soy flour is 4800.00 mg/100 g, which is 85% higher than in wheat flour and 77% higher than in buckwheat flour.

Cu (copper), as part of many enzymes and biologically active metalloproteins, participates in tissue respiration processes, as well as the synthesis of collagen and elastin. The copper content in soy flour is 1342.00 mg/100 g, which is 92% higher than in wheat flour and 72% higher than in buckwheat flour.

Mn (manganese) is essential for the proper development of cells. The manganese content in soy flour is 2370.00 mg/100 g, which is 75% higher than in wheat flour and 68% higher than in buckwheat flour.

Ca (calcium) is an important element involved in the main physiological and biochemical processes of cells. The calcium content in soy flour is 280.00 mg/100 g, which is 93% higher than in wheat flour and 85% higher than in buckwheat flour.

Mg (magnesium) is a key participant in energy processes, nerve-muscle communication, and muscle contraction mechanisms. The magnesium content in soy flour is 431.00 mg/100 g, which is 96% higher than in wheat flour and 88% higher than in buckwheat flour.

K (potassium) helps normalize heart rhythm, maintains the acid-base balance of blood, and prevents the accumulation of sodium salts. The potassium content in soy flour is 894.30 mg/100 g, which is 86% higher than in wheat flour and 85% higher than in buckwheat flour.

P (phosphorus) is one of the essential substances for life. It is present in all tissues, especially in muscles and the brain, and participates in metabolic processes. Phosphorus is also crucial for the normal functioning of the nervous system and heart muscles. The phosphorus content in soy flour is 706.00 mg/100 g, which is 87% higher than in wheat flour and 64% higher than in buckwheat flour.

S (sulfur) increases the body's resistance to radiation, helps bile secretion, ensures good blood circulation, and assists in detoxification. The sulfur content in buckwheat flour is 81.00 mg/100 g, which is 13% higher than in wheat flour. This element is absent in soy flour.

Conclusion. The results of studying the nutritional value of high-quality wheat, buckwheat, and soy flours revealed the unique advantages of these raw materials. While the protein, fat, and fiber content in high-quality wheat flour is relatively low, it is enriched with starch and easily digestible carbohydrates. Buckwheat flour stands out due to its low glycemic index, gluten-free composition, and high protein content. Soy flour has the highest protein and fat content, and it is an important nutritional source for the body due to its omega-3 and omega-6 fatty acids, B vitamins, and microelements.

In terms of fiber content, soy flour leads, enhancing its ability to cleanse and detoxify the body. Buckwheat flour, rich in beneficial amino acids, including asparagine acid, and minerals, is another nutritious option. In terms of vitamins and microelements, soy flour has a clear advantage, especially for minerals such as calcium, magnesium, zinc, and iron.

The research results open up possibilities for combining these three raw materials to create products with high nutritional value that are healthy and beneficial.

REFERENCES

1. Morris C.E., Sands D.C. The natural genetic engineering of plants and the origins of plant-based foods. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 2019.
2. Shahidi F., Zhong Y. Lipid oxidation and improving the oxidative stability. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 2020.
3. FAO/WHO Joint Expert Committee on Food Additives (JECFA). Safety Evaluation of Certain Food Additives and Contaminants. WHO Technical Report, Geneva, 2020.
4. Matveeva T.V., Nikitin D.M. Technology of soy-based product production. Moscow: KolosS, 2019.
5. Kharchenko V.A. Biochemistry of grain-based products. St. Petersburg: GIORD, 2017.
6. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on "Food Product Safety." Tashkent, 2022.
7. Codex Alimentarius Commission. General Standards for Food Additives. FAO/WHO, Rome, 2021.